

Table 1. Biological interface between myositis and radiation-related muscle injury

Domain	Autoimmune or cancer-associated myositis	Radiation-related muscle injury	Diagnostic implication
Immune activation	Immune-mediated skeletal muscle injury involves innate and adaptive immune pathways; clinicoserological heterogeneity is partly defined by myositis-specific autoantibodies (32-34)	Ionising radiation induces inflammatory signalling through DNA damage, oxidative stress, cytokine release, and local immune modulation (21, 35-37, 44-47)	Shared inflammatory pathways may complicate attribution of muscle symptoms arising during cancer treatment
Antigen exposure	In cancer-associated myositis, tumour-driven loss of self-tolerance and immune cross-reactivity between tumour and muscle antigens are plausible mechanisms (33, 34)	Radiation-induced tissue injury may enhance local antigen release and antigen presentation within the irradiated field (44-47)	Biological overlap may support diagnostic uncertainty, but does not imply mechanistic equivalence
Interferon signalling	Type I interferon pathways are implicated in several inflammatory myopathy subsets and may contribute to disease phenotype (32)	cGAS-STING activation after irradiation may promote type I interferon signalling, with modulation by dose and fractionation (44, 45)	Interferon biology represents a plausible interface between radiation response and autoimmune susceptibility
Microvascular injury	Complement-mediated microangiopathy is a recognised feature in subsets of inflammatory myopathy, particularly dermatomyositis (32)	Endothelial apoptosis, capillary rarefaction, impaired perfusion, and tissue hypoxia are central components of radiation injury (35, 37)	Convergent vascular injury may contribute to overlapping clinical and imaging features
Fibrosis and remodelling	Chronic inflammation may lead to muscle damage, fatty replacement, weakness, and functional impairment (32, 62, 65)	Persistent hypoxia and transforming growth factor- β -driven fibroatrophy underlie late radiation fibrosis and chronic tissue remodelling (20, 38-41)	Distinguishing active inflammation from chronic structural damage is essential for management
Distribution	More often systemic, diffuse, multifocal, or symmetric; extramuscular manifestations may be present depending on disease subset (32-34)	Usually confined to the irradiated field, or to previously irradiated tissue in recall syndromes (20, 22, 28-31, 49)	Anatomical distribution is one of the most useful differentiating clues in clinical practice
Relation to tumour behaviour	May precede, accompany, or follow cancer diagnosis; in paraneoplastic disease, manifestations may parallel tumour activity (8-11, 27, 33, 34)	Usually related to radiotherapy timing, field distribution, or subsequent drug exposure in recall syndromes (20, 22, 28-31)	Temporal relation to tumour evolution and treatment sequence helps refine diagnostic attribution

Footnote: Data are synthesised qualitatively from the cited literature and are intended as an interpretive summary rather than as guideline-level evidence

Abbreviations: cGAS, cyclic GMP-AMP synthase; STING, stimulator of interferon genes; TGF- β , transforming growth factor- β .

Table 2. Differential diagnosis of muscle symptoms after breast radiotherapy

Feature	Radiation-induced inflammatory myopathy	Radiation recall myositis	Autoimmune myositis flare	Paraneoplastic or cancer-associated myositis
Clinical context	Symptoms arise during or after radiotherapy within irradiated tissues	Symptoms arise after exposure to a systemic agent administered following prior radiotherapy	Symptoms occur in a patient with known autoimmune myositis or a compatible autoimmune phenotype	Symptoms occur in temporal association with breast cancer diagnosis, recurrence, or progression
Trigger	Radiotherapy itself	Systemic therapy after prior radiotherapy; reported triggers include gemcitabine, paclitaxel, carboplatin, pazopanib, and sunitinib (22, 28-31)	Underlying autoimmune disease activity, with or without interaction with cancer treatment	Underlying malignancy and tumour-host immune interaction (27, 33, 34)
Timing	During radiotherapy or after treatment; may evolve from acute inflammatory injury to later fibroatrophic change (20, 21, 35-43)	After administration of the triggering systemic agent following radiotherapy (22, 28-31)	Independent of radiotherapy timing; may pre-date, coexist with, or follow cancer treatment (32)	Usually temporally related to cancer onset, recurrence, or progression (8-11, 33, 34)
Distribution	Confined to the irradiated field	Confined to previously irradiated tissues	More often diffuse, multifocal, or symmetric proximal muscle involvement	Usually systemic rather than field-confined; may parallel tumour behaviour
Systemic manifestations	Usually absent or limited	Usually absent outside the recall field	May include rash, interstitial lung disease, arthritis, dysphagia, or other systemic manifestations depending on subset (32)	May include dermatomyositis skin manifestations and other extramuscular features
Autoantibodies	Not expected to define the syndrome	Not expected to define the syndrome	Often informative for classification and phenotype definition (32)	Anti-TIF1 γ and, in selected cases, anti-NXP2 may support suspicion of malignancy-associated disease (11-14)
MRI pattern	Focal oedema, fatty change, or fibrosis confined to the treatment field (22, 49)	Field-restricted inflammatory abnormalities in previously irradiated tissue (22, 28, 31, 49)	Diffuse, multifocal, or symmetric inflammatory changes are more typical (32, 49)	Usually systemic rather than field-restricted; interpreted together with tumour context and serology
FDG PET-CT pattern	Localised uptake may support field-confined injury (22, 49)	Localised uptake within the prior radiation field after a systemic trigger (22, 28, 31, 49)	Diffuse or multifocal muscular uptake may suggest systemic inflammatory disease (49, 63, 64)	Diffuse or multifocal uptake may raise suspicion for systemic or paraneoplastic disease; oncological interpretation remains essential (25, 33, 49)

Immediate diagnostic priority	Confirm field concordance and exclude systemic autoimmune disease	Identify the temporal relation with the triggering systemic agent and prior radiation field	Assess disease activity, extramuscular involvement, and current immunomodulatory treatment	Evaluate tumour status, recurrence risk, and whether symptom evolution parallels cancer behaviour
Main management priority	Supportive care, rehabilitation, symptom monitoring, and prevention of long-term functional impairment (20, 23, 49)	Reassess the implicated systemic therapy and coordinate oncological management	Control autoimmune inflammation according to established IIM treatment principles (32, 62, 65)	Control the underlying malignancy while managing systemic inflammatory manifestations (27, 33, 34)

Footnote: Differential diagnosis should integrate treatment timing, anatomical distribution, imaging pattern, systemic manifestations, serology, and tumour behaviour

Abbreviations: FDG, fluorodeoxyglucose; IIM, idiopathic inflammatory myopathy; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; PET-CT, positron emission tomography-computed tomography; TIF1 γ , transcription intermediary factor 1 gamma; NXP2, nuclear matrix protein 2.

Table 3. Practical principles for radiotherapy and multidisciplinary care

Clinical scenario	Main risk issue	Practical radiotherapy implication	Multidisciplinary management principle
Pre-existing quiescent autoimmune myositis	Potentially increased susceptibility to treatment-related toxicity, although direct evidence remains limited and largely indirect (43, 56-61)	Radiotherapy should not be considered an automatic contraindication; treatment may be delivered with careful individualisation and modern conformal planning where appropriate (50, 59-61)	Establish baseline disease activity, review extramuscular involvement, and coordinate with rheumatology before treatment initiation
Active autoimmune myositis at the time of radiotherapy decision-making	Greater concern for toxicity, diagnostic ambiguity, and treatment interruption if symptoms worsen during therapy	Whenever feasible, radiotherapy should be planned during a phase of greater disease stability; dose to muscle and other susceptible normal tissues should be minimised as far as clinically possible (50, 60-62)	Joint decision-making among radiation oncology, rheumatology, and medical oncology is essential; immunomodulatory treatment should be optimised according to overall oncological timing
New field-confined muscle symptoms during or after radiotherapy	Risk of misclassifying local radiation-related injury as systemic autoimmune disease	Evaluate the relation to treatment field, treatment timing, and expected radiation-related tissue effects before attributing symptoms to autoimmune flare	Clinical examination, serum creatine kinase and aldolase, and MRI-based pattern recognition should guide initial assessment; early rehabilitation input may be useful
New symptoms after systemic therapy in a previously irradiated area	Risk of overlooking radiation recall myositis and continuing a triggering agent without reassessment	Review prior radiation field and systemic treatment sequence carefully; radiotherapy history is central to diagnosis	Medical oncology and radiation oncology should jointly reassess the suspected trigger, oncological priorities, and symptom severity
Diffuse or systemic muscle symptoms during breast cancer treatment	Risk of under-recognising autoimmune flare or paraneoplastic disease when symptoms occur near radiotherapy	Radiotherapy-related attribution should not rely on timing alone; field distribution and systemic features are critical	Rheumatological evaluation, autoantibody assessment, MRI, and selective FDG PET-CT may help distinguish systemic disease from local toxicity
Suspected paraneoplastic or cancer-associated myositis	Risk of delaying oncological reassessment if symptoms are attributed only to treatment toxicity	Radiotherapy decisions should be integrated with tumour status rather than considered in isolation	Oncological restaging, serological stratification, and multidisciplinary reassessment are required; tumour control remains a central therapeutic objective
Chronic post-radiotherapy pain, stiffness, or functional restriction	Risk of interpreting late fibroatrophic change as ongoing active myositis	Late symptoms should be interpreted in the context of prior dose distribution, chronic fibrosis, and radiation fibrosis syndrome (20, 38-41)	Management should include rehabilitation, functional assessment, and selective imaging to distinguish chronic structural damage from active inflammation

Any diagnostically uncertain scenario	Risk of overtreatment with immunosuppression or undertreatment of clinically significant autoimmune disease	Radiotherapy planning and post-treatment interpretation should be embedded in an integrated clinical framework rather than a single-specialty approach	Final attribution should integrate timing, field distribution, autoantibody profile, imaging pattern, tumour behaviour, and multidisciplinary discussion
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Footnote: Recommendations are based on limited and heterogeneous evidence and should be interpreted within an individualised multidisciplinary framework

Abbreviations: FDG, fluorodeoxyglucose; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging.